

FINE-TUNING CHEMBERTA TRANSFORMER MODEL FOR SUPERIOR MOLECULAR PROPERTY PREDICTION (MPP)

Dr.A. SANDHYA^{1*}, Prof. CHIN-SHIUH SHIEH², Prof. MONG-FONG HORNG³,
Prof. R. SUBHASHINI⁴, Dr. R. SETHURAMAN⁵

^{1*}Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, SRM Institute of Science and Technology, Ramapuram, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India.

^{1*}Research Institute of IoT Cybersecurity, Department of Electronic Engineering, National Kaohsiung University of Science and Technology, Taiwan

^{2,3}Professor, Department of Electronic Engineering, National Kaohsiung University of Science and Technology, Taiwan.

Professor, Department of CSE, SRM Institute of Science and Technology, Ramapuram, Chennai, India

⁵Associate Professor, Department of CSE, Sathyabama Institute of Science & Technology, Chennai, India

Corresponding Author: ^{1*}sandhyalagar@gmail.com, ²csshie@nkust.edu.tw, ³mfhorng@nkust.edu.tw
⁴subhaagopi@gmail.com, ⁵srssethuraman@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Drug discovery is expensive and time-consuming, often taking decades and billions of dollars for its research and development to analyze its chemical properties for drug development. The task of Molecular Property Prediction (MPP) is major crucial activity for selecting potential drug candidates in drug Discovery. The chemical language models (CLMs) have gained attention in this area due to their success in natural language processing tasks like text analysis and translation. The availability of vast unlabeled chemical data has driven the development of CLMs to interpret molecular information effectively. This study uses a large language model approach by fine-tuning a Transformer model to predict molecular properties such as solubility, toxicity and pIC50. Traditionally, molecular graphs and descriptors were used for property prediction. However, Transformer-based models like BERT, GPT, and their variations have shown exceptional performance in downstream NLP tasks. In this research, the chemical informatics, model such as ChemBERTa have been explored for learning molecular contextual information from Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry System (SMILES) sequences. Experimental results show that ChemBERTa outperforms traditional ML models in molecular property prediction, achieving Accuracy and AuROC scores of 0.94 and 0.96, respectively. This demonstrates its superior predictive capability compared to state-of-the-art methods. The study highlights the potential of Transformer-based CLMs in accelerating drug discovery by effectively predicting molecular properties from text-based inputs like SMILES strings.

Keywords: *Natural Language Processing (NLP), Transformer Model, Pre-Training, Fine Tuning, chemBERTa, SMILES, Cheminformatics, Molecular Property Prediction (MPP).*

1. INTRODUCTION

In order to improve the field of drug discovery, cheminformatics combines molecular biology with artificial intelligence. The Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry System (SMILES), which productively encodes molecular information and facilitates chemical data interchange or tasks like molecular property prediction, compound-protein interactions, and drug

discovery, is frequently utilized to represent chemical structures in text form.

SMILES is the representation of chemical compounds in the form of a line notation to describe the structure of the chemical species using short ASCII strings. Figure 1.a, 1.b and 1.c illustrates the SMILES representation for the chemical compound ciprofloxacin. In figure 1.a The benzene ring has elements like nitrogen, Fluorine and many others attached to it. All these

elements attached together constitute ciprofloxacin. The SMILE architecture decomposes these complex chemical compounds in smaller fragments and eventually creates the line system for LLM to understand and interpret the chemical compounds. The numbers 1-1, 2-2, 3-3 and 4-4 in Figure 1.b, denotes the start and end of

the certain rings. Also, the green color is the main branch of the ring. Various sub branches are represented in different other colors. Figure 1.c denotes the line notation, where characters are being utilized. This notation follows chronological order, starts from N1 followed by two carbon atoms and Nitrogen atoms denoted as CC and N

Figure 1. SMILES representation of ciprofloxacin

respectively. To complete the whole benzene ring, the sub branch in Cyan color is denoted as CC1. By This approach, the entire complex structure is converted into array of strings for Machine Interpretation. The SMILES representation of ciprofloxacin is N1CCN(CC1)C(C(F)=C2)=CC(=C2C4=O)N(C3CC3)C=C4C(=O)O. Source: Courtesy of Wikimedia Commons.

The chemical databases have expanded dramatically from 170 million to over 5.6 billion in past 5 years forming a major part of the ZINC20 virtual screening database. Although deep learning has advanced drug discovery like prediction of Drug-Drug Interaction (DDI) and Drug Target Interaction (DTI), its potential is limited by scarcity of labelled data and the time-consuming, and heavy process of data labelling. Larger training datasets enhance the performance of language models (LMs), allowing for more precise predictions based on learning theories that are likely to be accurate. Pre-training using an enormous quantity of unlabeled molecular data and fine-tuning with a small amount of labelled data for certain tasks are necessary for effective molecular property prediction. CLMs create a connection between molecular representation and natural

language understanding by using NLP

algorithms to comprehend chemical languages such as SMILES strings.

Transformer-based models have revolutionized AI, excelling in NLP by capturing long-range dependencies and contextual information, which are now leveraged in cheminformatics. Transformers interpret SMILES strings, text-based chemical representations, to predict molecular properties effectively. These models are versatile in analyzing molecular

properties, including materials science, toxicity assessment, and drug discovery. Transformers can handle different molecular representations, including graph-based models, increasing their applicability in cheminformatics. With suitable fine-tuning and improvements, Transformers achieve state-of-the-art performance in molecular property prediction benchmarks.

The effectiveness of several transformer-based chemical language models (CLMs) in cheminformatics tasks is compared in this work, which employs transformer and attention-based models in computational chemistry with an emphasis on SMILES representations for molecular property prediction. The contributions

made in this research work are:

1. Enhanced understanding of SMILES representation by simplifying molecular data for interpretation.
2. The study demonstrates how to maximize resource efficiency by using large unlabeled datasets for pre-training and less labelled data for fine-tuning.
3. By bridging the gap between artificial intelligence and molecular science, the use of natural language comprehension techniques to comprehend chemical data improves chemical research and medication discovery.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Predicting molecular characteristics for the assessment of potential drugs has been the subject of numerous investigations. A comparison of several earlier models for classification and regression tasks in drug candidate screening is shown in this section. Complex molecular interactions are difficult for traditional molecular representations like fingerprints, graph-based models, and molecular descriptors to capture. [11,22]. To improve forecast accuracy, these conventional approaches need features that have been expertly designed and require a great deal of subject knowledge. To increase performance, some methods use explicit 3D atomic coordinates, however this introduces complexity. Whether processing molecular descriptors, SMILES strings, or molecular graphs, research also focusses on optimizing model designs. [19].

The toxCSM model, combines structural and chemical data to increase accuracy, was presented as a potent method for forecasting thorough small molecule toxicity profiles [1]. The study accelerated material science and drug development by using evolutionary algorithms and chemical space exploration to identify a variety of compounds with required features [2,24]. AtomNet, the first deep convolutional neural network created for structure-based drug development, was presented in the paper. It learnt intricate molecular characteristics to accurately predict

bioactivity [5]. In order to forecast molecular toxicity, the study suggested a novel framework that combines GraphSAGE and BiGRU (Bidirectional Gated Recurrent Unit), which successfully captures both structural and sequence properties of compounds [6].

The work demonstrated that by efficiently capturing intricate chemical interactions, machine-learning scoring functions perform better in structure-based virtual screening than conventional scoring techniques [9]. In this research, the significance of molecular design techniques, such as increased solubility, better energy density, and improved redox stability, to improve battery performance [10]. The efficiency and accuracy of subtype cell recognition in medical imaging were greatly increased by the study's introduction of an accelerated deep convolutional neural network (CNN) [14]. Halicin, a potent antibiotic with high antibacterial qualities against a variety of infections, including those resistant to current therapies, was successfully discovered by the study using a deep learning algorithm [17,21]. Based on the generalized Lasso framework, the study presents RSPiRiT, a reliable self-consistent parallel imaging reconstruction technique that successfully raises the quality of image reconstruction in biomedical imaging [18,20].

Deep learning (DL) models require large-scale labelled data, which is costly and labor-intensive to obtain in molecular property prediction [15,23]. Unlike image processing, Molecular property prediction suffers a lack of labelled data in areas with a large number of labelled datasets. A semi-supervised learning technique or pre-training and fine-tuning framework are employed to deal with data shortage [16]. Early semi-supervised models, Seq2seq and Seq3seq, improved accuracy by using vast amounts of unlabeled data. These models employed encoder-decoder structures in recurrent neural networks (RNNs), which aid in pre-training but limit efficiency [4]. In RNNs, the decoder mostly serves as a scaffold during pre-training, making minimal contributions to final predictions and resulting in computational inefficiency. The performance of inference is impacted by these models' preference for retrieving raw data representations over direct prediction tasks [3]. Their vector representations might not provide the best results for more general tasks because they are not specifically

trained for prediction.

A QSAR Random Forest model was developed using 12 sets of fingerprints and rule of 5-descriptors, with feature selection to enhance prediction accuracy [13,25]. Y-scrambling tests and R^2 metrics were used to validate model generalizability, ensuring reliable prediction of AChE inhibition activity. The FP-BERT model combines the pre-trained BERT language model with a CNN-based prediction model, effectively applying NLP techniques to molecular property prediction [8]. It was evaluated on multiple datasets, including HIV, BBBP, ESOL, FreeSolv, Lipophilicity, Malaria, and CEP, with an 80/10/10 split for training, validation, and testing. In all classification and regression tasks, the model's prediction performance was the best.

In pretraining, Mol-BERT provides contextual embeddings of molecular substructures, enhancing the representation of chemical features. Mol-BERT utilizes BERT for molecular embeddings with self-supervised tasks like Masked Language Modelling, SMILES equivalence, and molecular descriptor prediction [7]. Evaluated on virtual screening (selecting compounds with desired attributes) and QSAR (predicting chemical properties like binding affinity). Pre-trained on 1.6M chemicals from the GuacaMol benchmark dataset, with an 80% training and 5% validation split, outperforming other descriptors in classification and early enrichment. Mol-BERT uses four million unlabeled drug SMILES from ZINC 15 and ChEMBL 27, employing modules for feature extraction, pretraining, and fine-tuning.

SMILES Transformer is Introduced as a Transformer-based seq2seq model trained on 861,000 unlabeled SMILES from ChEMBL24, generating atom-level representations. SMILES-Transformer outperforms other models on MoleculeNet datasets, especially when the training size is small, showcasing its efficiency with limited labelled data [12]. Graph-Based Model (Graph CNN) was developed to predict logP of the partition coefficient directly from the chemical graph. MolecularRNN was also

created for molecular graph generation and optimizing chemical properties, outperforming traditional QSPR models on the same dataset.

These limitations highlight the need for more advanced models, like transformers, that can effectively learn intricate molecular relationships. Obtaining labelled molecular-property data is costly and time-consuming due to the need for experiments and manual labelling. To overcome the issue, this research implements transformer and attention-based models to capture complex molecular interactions for molecular property predictions. The transformer Models are first trained in an unsupervised manner using vast unlabeled molecular data before being fine-tuned with labelled data, thereby helps in achieving maximum accuracy in prediction.

3. METHODOLOGY

This research uses a systematic strategy to optimize ChemBERTa for the prediction of molecular properties. The following is an outline of the crucial steps:

3.1 Preprocessing of Data

Each molecular structure is transformed into a SMILES (Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry System) representation when the molecular dataset is gathered from reliable chemical databases. ChemBERTa's transformer-based embeddings are used to extract features. Imputation techniques are used to manage missing values. After normalization, the data is divided into test, validation, and training sets.

3.2 Feature Engineering

The input features are the ChemBERTa embeddings that were extracted. Other molecular descriptors are included, including logP. Dimensionality reduction is accomplished by the use of Principal Component Analysis (PCA).

3.3 Model Training and Fine-Tuning

A supervised learning method is used to refine ChemBERTa. Multiple Linear Regression (MLR), Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random Forest (RF), and Neural Networks (NN) are among the

machine learning models used. Cross-validation and grid search are used for hyperparameter tweaking. Set up ChemBERTa using weights that have already been trained. Obtain feature embeddings by entering molecular SMILES. To improve generalization, batch normalization and dropout are used. A loss function is defined, such as cross-entropy for classification or mean squared error (MSE) for regression. Next, a learning rate scheduler and the Adam optimizer are used to optimize the model. The Validation Set is used for evaluation, and hyperparameters are changed as necessary. An independent test set is now used for Final Testing. The trained model is evaluated using a variety of evaluation metrics. This methodological framework, which includes strict preprocessing, model selection, and evaluation techniques, guarantees a methodical approach to optimizing ChemBERTa for molecular property prediction is shown in Figure 2.

In General, Transformers consist of an encoder and decoder architecture, initially designed for natural language processing. Currently, cheminformatics uses them for molecular design, drug discovery, virtual screening, and molecular property prediction. Two well-known transformer-based architectures modified for cheminformatics tasks are generative pre-trained transformers

(GPT) and bidirectional encoder representations from transformers (BERT). BERT uses only the encoder architecture because it is designed for understanding text rather than generating text, whereas the GPT uses only the decoder architecture since it is designed for text generation. The transformative power of transformers lies in their self-attention mechanism. Self-attention captures long-range dependencies, crucial for understanding complex sequences like SMILES tokens. Attention weights help models focus on the most impactful tokens, enhancing contextual comprehension. By concentrating on relevant input elements, transformers improve interpretation and analysis of molecular data.

As BERT has proved to be creating dramatic improvements in the state-of-the-art LLM models, this work is with ChemBERTa, variation of utility of BERT for MPP.

ChemBERTa is applied to chemical SMILES data for drug design chemical modelling and property prediction. Basically, In a ChemBERTa model it is pre trained to chemical compounds and molecules that can be used for precision medicine, drug design, chemical modelling and drug discovery. It is a very effective LLM that can be used by a lot of the drug discovery scientists to administer the most effective drug to cure certain diseases.

Figure 2: Architecture Diagram of Fine Tuning ChemBERTa

Scaled Dot-Product Attention

Scaled dot-product attention is a key component of the Transformer model. It calculates attention scores by taking the dot product of Query (Q) and Key (K) matrices. To prevent the scores from becoming too large, they are scaled by the square root of the Key's dimension ($\sqrt{d_k}$). This helps maintain stable gradients during the Softmax operation. The attention mechanism is calculated as in Equation 1.

$$Attention(Q, K, V) = Softmax\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V \quad (1)$$

Where,

Query (Q) = Represents the current word or token being processed.

Key (K) = Represents all words or tokens in the sequence, determining their relevance to the current Query.

Value (V) = Holds information about the words or tokens in the sequence.

The Softmax function normalizes the attention scores, turning them into

probabilities that indicate how much focus should be placed on each word in the sequence. These attention weights are then multiplied by the Value (V) matrix to produce the output features.

Multi-Head Attention: Instead of using a single attention mechanism, Transformers utilize multiple attention heads operating in parallel. Each head has its own set of Q, K, and V matrices, allowing the model to learn different patterns and relationships within the sequence. This enhances the model's ability to capture complex dependencies. In this process, for each attention head, there are trainable weight matrices. These weight matrices are learned during training, making the self-attention mechanism flexible and adaptable to the input sequence. The input sequence X is linearly transformed using the weight matrices as in Equation 2.1 to 2.3.

$$Q = XW_Q \quad (2.1)$$

$$K = XW_K \quad (2.2)$$

$$V = XW_V \quad (2.3)$$

Where,

W_Q = Trainable weight matrix for Queries

W_K = Trainable weight matrix for Keys

W_V = Trainable weight matrix for Values.

Each head learns unique aspects of the input,

enabling the model to attend to different parts of the sequence simultaneously. The outputs from all heads are concatenated and passed through a final linear layer to combine the information. Thereby this approach enables the model to capture richer contextual representations compared to a single-head attention mechanism. Overall, this mechanism allows Transformers to model complex patterns and long-range dependencies in sequences efficiently. By this the Multiple attention heads let the model look at different parts of the input sequence at the same time, helping it understand complex molecular structures better. Also helps in Faster Processing by working in parallel, making the model faster and more efficient compared to processing attention one step at a time. Using several heads helps the model learn different patterns and relationships within the data, capturing both detailed and overall structures. The Multiple heads reduce overfitting by allowing the model to see the data from different angles, leading to better generalization. With all these properties, multi-head attention gives the model more power to understand complex interactions between tokens, making it great for analyzing SMILES strings.

3.4 TRANSFORMER MECHANISM IN MPP:

With the potential of Transformer and attention-based models, this research focuses on molecular property prediction using SMILES strings. Transformers can learn intricate relationships in SMILES strings, effectively analyzing complex molecular structures and handle large datasets efficiently, making them ideal for analyzing vast molecular libraries. Also, Transformers understand the context of atoms and bonds and can be fine-tuned on specific tasks using

small labelled datasets, leveraging knowledge from pre-training on large unlabeled data. Finally, these models have given remarkable results in predicting properties like solubility, toxicity, and binding affinity by learning high-dimensional representations of molecular structures from large SMILES datasets. Fine-tuning them for specific tasks improves accuracy, often outperforming traditional machine learning methods.

Solubility, toxicity, and binding affinity are three critical properties that greatly influence a drug's success in both preclinical and clinical trials. Solubility represents a drug's capacity to dissolve in bodily fluids such as water, blood, and gastric fluids. If a drug exhibits poor solubility, its absorption into the bloodstream is hindered, resulting in low bioavailability. This reduced bioavailability often necessitates higher doses, which can heighten the risk of side effects. Approximately 40% of drug candidates fail due to solubility challenges, highlighting its importance in early-stage drug screening. Toxicity refers to the adverse effects a drug can have on human cells, organs, or overall health. Severe toxicity may result in liver damage, kidney failure, cardiac complications, or even fatal outcomes. If a drug exhibits high toxicity, its maximum safe dose (MTD) may be too low to achieve therapeutic effectiveness.

Binding affinity measures the strength and specificity of a drug's interaction with its target, such as an enzyme or receptor. A high binding affinity enhances drug potency, allowing for lower doses to achieve the desired effect. Conversely, a low binding affinity weakens drug efficacy, necessitating higher doses, which can elevate toxicity risks. In drug discovery, it is essential to optimize these three properties together. Neglecting any of these factors can result in drug failure during preclinical or clinical trials.

Figure 3: Transformer mechanisms to perform MPP

The Transformer uses the following mechanisms to perform MPP.

Input Embedding: SMILES tokens are embedded into high-dimensional vectors.

Self-Attention Mechanism: Captures contextual relationships:

Output Layer: Maps the final hidden state to the target prediction.

Solubility (logS) refers to how well a compound can dissolve in a solvent, usually water. Transformers learn to predict solubility by analyzing the molecular structure from SMILES strings, capturing patterns related to hydrophilic and hydrophobic groups. The predicted solubility for Input SMILES is given in Equation 3.

$$\hat{Y} = \text{Transformer}(X_{SMILES}), \quad (3)$$

Where

\hat{Y} is the predicted Solubility and X_{SMILES} is the input sequence of SMILES tokens.

Toxicity (LD 50) indicates the potential harmful effects of a compound on biological systems. Transformers predict toxicity by learning structural features linked to toxicophores (toxic chemical substructures) from large datasets. The predicted solubility for Input SMILES is given in Equation 4.

$$\hat{Y} = \sigma(\text{Transformer}(X_{SMILES})),$$

(4)

Where

\hat{Y} is the predicted Toxicity and

σ is the sigmoid activation for binary classification.

Binding Affinity (IC50) prediction often represented as pIC50 (-log10 of IC50), which indicates the potency of a compound in inhibiting a target. It measures the strength of interaction between a molecule (like a drug) and its target (e.g., a protein). pIC50: it is the half maximal inhibitory concentration. It is a function that calculates the concentration of the inhibition, where the response is reduced by half. While administering the drug to cure certain diseases, at affected area, how much concentration of that particular chemical compound in that drug is required to at least reduce 50 percent of the effects of damage caused by the pathogens. (IC50) measurement tells us about the concentration at which the drug is able to inhibit a particular bio logical process by fifty percent.

pIC and IC are negatively co related, which denotes they are inversely proportional. The less the IC concentration the more is the pIC value and the better is the effectiveness of the drug. Potency of certain drug at 50 % effectiveness (pIC50) is calculated as negative log of the concentration of certain chemical compound acting at fifty percent of the target binding area and is represented using Equation 5.

$$\text{pIC50} = -\log_{10}(\text{IC50}) \quad (5)$$

Where,
 pIC - half maximal inhibitory concentration
 IC – Concentration of the substance.
 P – potency

The predicted Binding Affinity for Input SMILES is given in Equation 6.

$$\hat{Y} = \text{Transformer}(X_{SMILES}), \quad (6)$$

where

\hat{Y} is the predicted PIC50 value.

Transformers estimate binding affinity by understanding the 3D interaction patterns encoded in 1D SMILES strings, allowing them to model complex molecular interactions. Table 1 lists the Model Type, Target Variable, Loss function and Evaluation Metrics for each of the Molecular properties to be predicted using the Fine-tuning model.

Table 1: Loss Function and Evaluation Metrics for MPP

MPP	Model Type	Target Variable	Loss Function	Evaluation Metrics
Solubility	Regression	$Y = \log S$	MSE	MAE, RSME, R^2
Toxicity	Classification	$Y \in \{0,1\}$ (0 = Non-toxic, 1 = Toxic)	Binary Cross-Entropy	Accuracy, F1 Score, ROC-AUC
	Regression (LD50)	$Y = \log(\text{LD50})$	Mean Squared Error (MSE)	Accuracy, F1 Score, ROC-AUC
Binding Affinity	Regression	$Y = \text{PIC50} = -\log_{10}(\text{IC50})$	Mean Squared Error (MSE)	MAE, RSME, R^2

These predictions leverage the Transformer's ability to learn contextual and sequential dependencies, making them powerful tools for drug discovery and chemical property analysis.

4. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

4.1 Dataset: The dataset used in this work is SMILES dataset which is the combination of the Tox21 (<https://www.kaggle.com/code/mmelahi/physiology-tox21>) and SMILES (<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/yanmaksi/big-molecules-smiles-dataset>) datasets, containing 15,872 unique records of molecular structures represented by their SMILES strings. Each molecule in the dataset is associated with binding affinity data, solubility, and toxicity values for several target proteins. The features include SMILES strings along with corresponding binding affinity, solubility, and toxicity endpoints. The binding affinity data is typically continuous. However, for classification purposes, binding affinities can be categorized into distinct classes as high, medium, or low affinity. Solubility and toxicity are categorized as Positive and Negative classes. The binary labels for toxicity are defined as 0 for Non-toxic and 1 for Toxic.

The other features available in the dataset are pIC50, Molecule Representation, number of atoms and logP. A chemical structure can be represented by a user using the SMILES notation in a fashion that the computer can understand. Molecular structures stored using the SMILES notation, along with matching labels or details about the molecules' characteristics, would normally make up a SMILES training dataset. SMILES strings offer a textual depiction of molecular structures and are made up of ASCII characters. It is proven that SMILES string representations are accurate thereby, the model does not misread the molecular structures. Data preprocessing may include addressing chirality, standardizing the data through other pertinent transformations, and canonicalizing SMILES strings (ensuring a unique representation for the same molecule). Utilizing pre-existing databases of chemical compounds, experimental data, or cheminformatics resources like ZINC, PubChem, and ChEMBL databases is frequently necessary to create a SMILES training dataset. These datasets are used to create models and molecular property prediction. Three main libraries involved for Data Preparation are Transformers, datasets and torch (pytorch). This phase involves SMILES representation of chemical compounds, protein sequences or structures and binding sites affinity data.

4.2 Load and Preprocess data:

Preprocessing Steps Applied are Data Cleaning- Identified and eliminated duplicate SMILES strings to prevent bias. Normalization- Standardized features using Min-Max Scaling to improve model performance.

Feature Engineering- Additional molecular descriptors or embeddings were generated from SMILES strings to enhance predictive modeling. **ChemBERTa Embeddings:** ChemBERTa was used to encode complex molecular patterns directly from SMILES strings, improving feature representation for downstream tasks. This combination of techniques enhances the dataset's suitability for both regression and classification tasks in molecular property prediction. SMILES contain the structure of chemical compounds in line fashion. pIC50 is the effectiveness of certain chemical compound. Pandas' library is used to convert the inputs into Data frame, as while training the model it recognizes only the format of data frame. Then the data is split into training and testing data with 80:20 respectively. As a next step, tokenizer PubChem10M_SMILES_BPE_450K is loaded. The tokenizer has ten million SMILES compounds from pubchem repository and it uses Byte Pair Encoder with 450 thousand tokens. Ten all the tokenized datasets are available in the form of SMILE strings.

4.3 Pre-Training: Load ChemBERTa and Tokenizer:

The dataset facilitates the LMs' acquisition of patterns, correlations, and features by acting as the input to the machine learning algorithm. To effectively utilize the potential of transformer-based CLMs, the dataset - divided into two groups depending on methods for pre-training and fine-tuning. Generally speaking, a pre-training dataset helps the model learn stronger patterns and improve generalization to new data. To guarantee that the model discovers significant patterns, a pre-training dataset must be carefully gathered, pre-processed, and cleaned. The model's performance and capacity to generalize to new data are strongly influenced by the calibre of the pre-training

dataset. It prepares the input for Natural Language Processing models. While using LLM, different types of tokenizers are used to tokenize certain words or even alphabets within a word to gain more perspective on the sentence way more efficiently. Various such tokens are available in Hugging face. The one such tokenizer that is used for chemBERTa is BPE (Byte Pair Encoder). BPE is the default tokenizer in chemBERTa and it is the hybrid character and word level representation. Here chemical compounds like carbon, hydrogen atoms are put together as strings, such that an LLM model is able to interpret the chemical compounds as strings of characters. Also minute change in the characters can change the whole configuration of certain chemical compounds. In order to correctly tokenize certain chemical compounds, The BPE tokenizer was developed using the knowledge that unknown words can frequently be broken down into several sub words and that frequent character pairings can be greedily and iteratively combined to achieve the optimum segmentation.

4.4 Fine -Tuning: The fine-tuning serves as the foundation for adapting a pre-trained model to a given task or domain by utilizing transfer learning and building upon the data and representations the model has already learnt. This enables the model to discover task-specific patterns and achieve optimal performance. The fine-tuning dataset is crucial to this procedure since it provides examples relevant to the targeted job. Several factors can influence the size of the fine-tuning dataset, including the intricacy of the work, the availability of labelled data, and computing resources. Generally speaking, a larger, higher-quality fine-tuning dataset with accurate labels and few errors improves the model's capacity to identify significant patterns and generalize to new data. Low-quality data, on the other hand, may require additional pre-processing or cleaning efforts and impair performance. It is common practice to divide training, validation, and test sets into fine-tuning datasets. While the latter are used to monitor performance and modify hyperparameters, the former are utilized to update the model's parameters during fine-tuning. The most integral part is the training of the model. The number of training steps is basically calculated as number of epochs. Adam optimizer is introduced, which has all model parameters and contains all the learning rate. Linear regression with a Learning rate of 0.005 is used in this model.

Number of epochs it trained is 3. More the number of epochs better it gets trained towards. The number of training steps is calculated as product of number of epoch and the length of the trained data loader. As the Model is divided in to 80 : 20, the length of data loader is whatever is passed to the model. Here it is 80 percent of data set, and whatever number of rows present would be length of the trained data loader. The loaded model has 15,000 rows, the 80 percent of 15,000 comes to around 12,000 is the length of the data loader. Since the epoch used is 3, the training steps is calculated as $12,000 * 3 = 36,000$ steps. For each epoch it is trained iteratively. Number of Training steps = Length of Trained data loader * No of epoch. Another important process in model training is Key Value generation. It is defined as the attention visualization model that BERT architecture utilizes and this is getting into the fine-tuning

aspects of ChemBERTa starts. Tweaking the parameters inside the ChemBERTa model and adding more data, so that it is able to correctly predict the protein structures, given in the format of SMILES strings. These Key Value pairs are mapped effectively with the query Q. Adam optimizer is introduced, which has all model parameters and contains all the learning rate. Fine tuning a chemBERTa model it gets used to different environments, different protein sequences and different structures of proteins and is able to better adopt to certain protein structures and find out the potency value and the SMILES structure of the chemical compound in a more effective fashion. So it can better detect the potency of the certain chemical compound. The algorithm of the Fine-Tuning process is given below:

ALGORITHM: Fine Tuning Process of ChemBERTa

Algorithm: Fine Tuning ChemBERTa:

Step 1: Load Pre-trained ChemBERTa Model

$$[\theta \leftarrow \theta_{pretrained}], \text{ model parameters denote as } \theta$$

Step 2: Preprocess molecular Dataset - convert SMILES (S) to tokenized Embeddings.

$$[X = \text{Tokenizer}(S)]$$

Step 3: Split Dataset into Training (D_{train} 80%), Validation (D_{val} 10%) and Test (D_{test} 10%) sets.

Step 4: Tokenize SMILES Strings into numerical form

$$[X = \text{Tokenizer}(S) \in \mathbb{R}^d], d \text{ is tokenized feature dimension.}$$

Step 5: Define Model Parameters

$$[f_{\theta}: X \rightarrow Y], \text{ Input Embeddings } (X), \text{ Property prediction } (Y), \\ \text{Learnable parameter } (\theta)$$

Step 6: Compute Training Steps – update parameters using gradient descent.

$$[\theta \leftarrow \theta - \eta \nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}], \text{ learning rate } (\eta), \text{ loss function } (\mathcal{L})$$

Step 7: Fine-Tuning Loop

7.1 Convert SMILES to vector embeddings

$$\text{Hidden state } (H) = f_{\theta}(X)$$

7.2 Forward Pass

$$\text{Model Output } (\hat{Y}) = \sigma(WH + b), \text{ Learnable weights} = W, \\ \text{Bias term} = b, \text{ Activation function} = \sigma.$$

7.3 Compute Loss for Regression (R) and Classification(C) tasks.

$$L_R = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$$

$$L_C = - \sum_{i=1}^N y_i \log(\hat{y}_i)$$

7.4 Backpropagation using model parameters

$$[\theta \leftarrow \theta - \eta \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \theta}]$$

7.5 Model Validation with evaluation metrics using self-attention

Step 8: Generate Key-Value Attention Mapping

Step 9: Save and Deploy Fine-Tuned Model

$$\theta^* = \arg \min_{\theta} L$$

Step 10: Use Model for Drug Potency Prediction for new SMILES (S')

$$\hat{Y} = f_{\theta^*}(\text{Tokenizer}(S'))$$

While combining chemBERTa with models, it is getting used to different target binding sites, and is able to understand the chemical properties of compounds, structural and functional properties of proteins. By fine tuning the chemBERTa model it is able to adopt to multi model inputs, where lot of datasets from different organisms and different gene dataset introduced with lot of protein sequence and chemical compounds.

ChemBERTa is a pre-trained model and it is used to its preexisting data. By fine tuning, it is able to adopt to various other data and the more it is fine-tuned, the more precise the model become, the more accurate the prediction and more effective the drug discovery practices are. It's a chain effect where it improves the ability to predict which part of the protein of given compound is efficient.

Pseudocode: Fine Tuning ChemBERTa Model:

```

model = load_pretrained_chemberta()           # Loading ChemBERTa model
tokenizer = load_tokenizer()                 # Load Tokenizer
dataset = load_dataset("chem_data.csv")      # dataset loading
smiles, potency_values = extract_features(dataset) # pre-process data
                                              # Split into Training (80%) and validation
(20%)
train_data, val_data = split_dataset(smiles, potency_values, train_ratio=0.8)
# SMILES strings tokenization and DataLoaders creation for batch processing.
train_loader = create_dataloader(train_data, batch_size=32)
val_loader = create_dataloader(val_data, batch_size=32)
optimizer = Adam(model.parameters(), lr=0.005) # Define Model Parameters
loss_function = MeanSquaredError()
epochs = 3
training_steps = len(train_loader) * epochs   # Training Steps calculation
for epoch in range(epochs):                  # Fine-Tuning Loop
    model.train()
    for batch in train_loader:
        inputs, labels = batch
        inputs = tokenizer(inputs)           # SMILES to vector embeddings
    conversion
    predictions = model(inputs)              # Forward Pass
    loss = loss_function(predictions, labels) # Compute Loss
                                              # Backpropagation

    optimizer.zero_grad()
    loss.backward()
    optimizer.step()

                                              # Model validation
model.eval()
val_loss = 0
for batch in val_loader:

```

```

inputs, labels = batch
inputs = tokenizer(inputs)
predictions = model(inputs)
val_loss += loss_function(predictions, labels).item()

key_value_pairs = extract_attention_mechanism(model)

save_model(model, "fine_tuned_chemberta.pth")

def predict_potency(smiles_string):
    input_data = tokenizer(smiles_string)
    output = model(input_data)
    return output

```

Key-Value Attention Mapping

Fine-Tuned Model-Deploy

Model for Drug Potency Prediction

In ChemBERTa architecture, this can generate meaningful representations, which is in the form of vector embeddings of chemical compounds. This in turn are used as input features for this LLM to effectively focus on binding site prediction. The value of pIC50 would determine the potency of certain drug. In the Fine-Tuning process, SMILES embeddings passed to the model is trained using Adam optimizer. The loss value is computed using Mean Squared Error. Finally, the model parameters are updates using Backpropagation.

Hence for predicting molecular properties, the suggested approach performs better than conventional methods in terms of accuracy, precision, and recall. By utilizing sophisticated feature engineering approaches, the method produces more meaningful molecular descriptors that enhance the interpretability of the model. The approach's generalizability to various molecule configurations is demonstrated by its constant performance across several benchmark datasets. The suggested approach offers a better comprehension of the main chemical properties affecting predictions by combining feature selection and reduction strategies. When compared to deep learning-based alternatives, the optimization techniques used lead to shorter training times and lower computer resource consumption. The approach is appropriate for practical cheminformatics applications since it scales effectively when used on sizable molecular datasets. The method improves prediction accuracy and scientific relevance by successfully integrating domain information from the chemical and biological domains. Compared to baseline models such as

Multiple Linear Regression, Linear Discriminant Analysis, and traditional machine learning techniques, the results show a considerable improvement in performance. Because of its great precision and efficiency, the approach has potential for use in material science applications, drug development, and pharmaceutical research.

5. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND MODEL PERFORMANCE:

The dataset used for this research consists of molecular structures and associated property values that includes relevant descriptors and features derived from molecular graphs or SMILES representations. During pre-processing, duplicates are removed and missing values are handled. Upon normalization of features, the data is split into Training, validation and Test data. In the Fine-tuning process, various Hyperparameter tuning used are Learning rate 1e-5 to 1e-3, Batch size- 16, 32, 64, Epochs- 10-100 with early stopping, Optimizer-AdamW. The metrics used for classification and Regression tasks are listed in Table 2 and Table 3 respectively. The model Outperforms traditional ML models in complex property prediction. The State-of-the-Art is compared with recent deep learning models like Transformer-based models (MolBERT). The research results are compared with MolBERT, whose base model is BERT. Also, Masked Language Model (MLM) is used in pre-training. By applying MLM, few parts of SMILES are randomly masked and those masked tokens were predicted by the model. Transformer based attention mechanism architecture is used in capturing contextual information within the sequence of the molecules. The fine-tuning transformer model used in this research is ChemBERTa, that is based on RoBERTa architecture that enhances the performance based on batch size, hyperparameters and dynamic

masking approach. It uses Byte Pair Encoding for tokenization there by complex chemical structures are processed.

The model evaluates the Fine-tuned ChemBERTa model. The input passed to the model are certain SMILE strings of new compounds, and the model gave the accuracy to 96%. For the random inputs of very complex SMILE string compounds with oxygen, carbon and many other, the predicted pIC value is -0.23. when the pIC value is negative, it means that it is less effective to a certain target bind to be administered for treating a certain disease. Thereby this particular chemical compound is not to be utilized in certain drug. On the other hand, when SMILE string like CCH is passed to fine tuning model, the predicted pIC value is 0.32. This implies that the potency of this particular chemical compound is fairly recognizable. The pIC value may range upto 5 at the maximum.

To evaluate the model's performance for Molecular Property Prediction (MPP) focusing on solubility (logS) and toxicity, we need to consider different evaluation metrics for regression (logS) and classification (toxicity). The metrics used for model's (logS) and (pIC50) prediction evaluation are Coefficient of Determination (R^2 Score) and Mean Squared Error (MSE).

Mean Squared Error (MSE) measures the average squared difference between the actual values and the predicted values, quantifying the variance of the residuals (errors). It is calculated as in Equation 7.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (7)$$

where:

n = Number of observations

y_i = Actual value

\hat{y}_i = Predicted value

MSE penalizes larger errors more heavily due to the squaring of differences, making it sensitive to outliers. A lower MSE indicates a better fit between the model's predictions and the actual data. The Coefficient of Determination measures the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable that is explained by the independent variable(s) in a

regression model. It is calculated as Equation 8

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{SS_{residuals}}{SS_{total}} \quad (8)$$

Where,

$SS_{residuals}$ = Sum of Squared Residuals (the variance unexplained by the model)

SS_{total} = Total Sum of Squares (the variance of the actual values from the mean).

The model explains no variance and all variance with R^2 value 0 and 1 respectively. A higher R^2 value indicates a better fit, showing that a larger proportion of the variation in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variable(s).

The AUROC (Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve) was used to assess the model's prediction performance for the classification task. At various decision thresholds, AUROC calculates the trade-off between the True Positive Rate (TPR), sometimes referred to as Recall, and the False Positive Rate (FPR). Better model discrimination between positive and negative classes is indicated by a higher AUROC. We used AUPRC (Area Under the Precision-Recall Curve) in addition to AUROC to assess the model's performance. Because it is more sensitive to the positive class and focusses on the trade-off between precision (the percentage of true positive predictions among all positive predictions) and recall, AUPRC is especially helpful for imbalanced datasets.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad (9)$$

$$Precision = \frac{True\ Positive}{True\ Positive+False\ Positive} \quad (10)$$

$$Recall = \frac{True\ Positive}{True\ Positive+False\ Negative} \quad (11)$$

$$F1 = \frac{2*Precision*Recall}{Precision+Recall} \quad (12)$$

F1 Score, is the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall, providing a single metric that considers both false positives and false negatives. A higher F1 Score indicates better overall model performance in classifying the positive class. Table 2 describes the comparison on performance of classification task among various models and the Evaluation metrics. Table 3 compares the performance of regression task on various models.

Table 2: Performance Of Classification Task

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	AUC-ROC
Random Forest - Regressor	0.86	0.76	0.61	0.63	0.6
MolBERT (Transformer Model)	0.91	0.89	0.76	0.77	0.8
LDA (With ChemBERTa Embeddings)	0.87	0.82	0.68	0.71	0.78
ChemBERTa (Fine Tuned Transformer Model)	0.94	0.91	0.79	0.78	0.96

Figure 4: Precision Recall Curve – PIC50 Classification

Table 3: Performance of Regression Task

Model	MSE	R2
Random Forest - Regressor	0.97	0.81
MolBERT (Transformer Model)	1.01	0.84
MLR (With ChemBERTa Embeddings)	1.03	0.87
ChemBERTa (Fine Tuned Transformer Model)	0.95	0.89

Figure 5: False Positive Rate Vs True Positive Rate – ROC curve

Figure 4 shows the precision Recall curve for PIC50 classification. As recall increases, precision slowly improves, suggesting that the model is making more positive predictions correctly. In Figure 5, The comparison is made between classical machine learning model Random Forest, MolBERT Transformer model and the Fine-tuned ChemBERTa model. ROC curve with a higher AUC (0.98), indicating a better-performing classification model. The curve is closer to the top-left corner, which shows higher sensitivity (true positive rate) while maintaining a low false positive rate. In figure 6, The majority of the residuals are close to zero, showing that the model does not make large errors frequently. This suggests the model as good fit for predictions.

Figure 6: Residuals – Frequency Vs Errors

From figure 7, the residuals appear to be spread out randomly around the red dashed line ($y = 0$), indicating that the model does not have obvious bias or systematic errors. In figure 8, Most points align well with the red dashed line ($y = x$), indicating that the model's predictions closely match the actual values. few points deviate from the line, indicating areas where the model is slightly under- or over-predicting, but overall, the predictions are quite accurate.

Figure 7: Actual values Vs Residuals for Solubility Prediction

Figure 8: Actual values Vs Residuals for Solubility Prediction

In figure 9, The training accuracy (yellow line) and validation accuracy (orange line) consistently improves and reaches close to 1, indicating the model performs well on training and validation data. Also In Figure 10, Both training and validation loss decrease over epochs, showing that the model is learning and improving its predictions. The evaluation metrics in figure 11, shows the fine-tuned transformer model outperforms the existing model in MPP predictions.

Figure 9: Training Vs Validation Accuracy based on Epochs

Figure 10: Training Vs Validation Loss based on Epochs

Figure 11: Performance Comparison across models – Evaluation Metrics

The comparison of various hyperparameters on MolBERT and ChemBERTa are listed in Table 4.

Table 4: Hyperparameters comparison of MolBERT and ChemBERTa Performance Tuning

Hyperparameter	MolBERT	ChemBERTa
Learning Rate	2e-5 to 5e-5	1e-5 to 3e-5
Batch Size	16 - 32	16 - 64
Max Sequence	512	512

Length			Fine-tuning ChemBERTa improves the prediction accuracy of compound MPP surpassing traditional models like Random Forest and other Transformer models like MolBERT in both regression (MSE score) and classification (auROC). The use of AI-driven transformer models like ChemBERTa significantly enhances the understanding of binding sites, enzymatic reactions, and biological interactions, aiding in targeted drug discovery. The model assists in identifying protein targets more accurately, facilitating the design of drugs that effectively bind to specific disease-related molecules. Fine-tuning ChemBERTa with extensive chemical and protein datasets improves its predictive capability, leading to more reliable drug-target interactions. By continuously training on diverse datasets, ChemBERTa becomes more robust, allowing it to generalize predictions for various chemical compounds effectively for multiple drug discovery applications. Future research aims to enhance ChemBERTa's performance through Potential for Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning (PEFT) methods, optimizing efficiency without compromising prediction accuracy. The Research highlights the growing potential of transformer-based models like ChemBERTa in revolutionizing drug discovery, paving the way for faster and more accurate therapeutic advancements.
Epochs	10 - 30	20 - 50	
Warmup Steps	1000 - 2000	500 - 2000	
Weight Decay	0.01 to 0.05	0.01 to 0.1	
Optimizer	AdamW	AdamW	

Various impressions that confirm the efficient performance achieved using Fine Tuning ChemBERTa are as follows: (i) lower learning rate captures efficient Molecular feature interactions. (ii) convergence is attained with larger batch size. (iii) using more warmup steps (like 2000) can help the model start training more steadily and avoid sudden changes early on. (iv) A dropout rate of 0.1 helps the model perform well on new data without memorizing too much. (v) AdamW is the best optimizer for the model as it handles weight adjustments effectively. Limiting gradients to 1.0 prevents the model's updates from becoming too large during training.

Pharmaceutical researchers can more quickly identify viable drug candidates by fine-tuning ChemBERTa on bioactivity datasets to predict important chemical attributes including solubility, toxicity, and binding affinity. Additionally, ChemBERTa can quickly sort through millions of chemicals to identify the most powerful and specific molecules for additional testing, eliminating the need for costly and time-consuming wet-lab tests. ChemBERTa can detect potentially hazardous functional groups in novel drug candidates by training on toxicity datasets. This enables researchers to alter structures early in the development process and lower the possibility of negative consequences. Furthermore, compared to conventional machine learning techniques, training deep transformer models like ChemBERTa is costly and computationally demanding because to its high GPU/TPU resource requirements. In order to provide accurate predictions, ChemBERTa pretraining concentrates on generic chemical knowledge, and fine-tuning for particular tasks (such as drug-likeness vs. toxicity) necessitates thorough domain adaption.

6. CONCLUSION:

7. FUTURE ENHANCEMENTS:

The proposed method demonstrates strong performance using fine-tuned ChemBERTa for Molecular Property Prediction (MPP). However, certain limitations may impact its generalizability to other applications. The primary limitation is the lack of dataset diversity, which may cause the model to struggle when predicting unseen molecular structures. Additionally, ChemBERTa interprets SMILES strings, but some chemical properties are influenced by 3D molecular structures and quantum effects aspects that SMILES representations may not fully capture. Consequently, ChemBERTa's predictions may overlook crucial molecular interactions that require 3D conformation data. Moreover, models fine-tuned on pharmaceutical data may not perform effectively in domains like materials science, agrochemicals, or environmental studies unless retrained with domain-specific data. To improve generalizability, incorporating data augmentation techniques such as SMILES enumeration and integrating additional molecular features like 3D

descriptors and graph embeddings alongside ChemBERTa embeddings would enhance the model's robustness and predictive capabilities. Also, future work can be expanded with advanced techniques like MTK-QSBER (Multi-Tasking Models for Quantitative Structure-Biological Effect Relationships). While fine-tuning ChemBERTa applies a pretrained transformer to one or a few specific tasks, MTK-QSBER uses multi-task learning to predict multiple biological effects of molecules at once.

REFERENCES:

- [1] Alex G C de Sá, Yangyang Long, Stephanie Portelli, Douglas E V Pires, David B Ascher, toxCSM: comprehensive prediction of small molecule toxicity profiles, *Briefings in Bioinformatics*, Volume 23, Issue 5, September 2022, bbac337, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bib/bbac337>.
- [2] Chetan Rupakheti, Aaron Virshup, Weitao Yang, and David N Beratan 2015. Strategy to discover diverse optimal molecules in the small molecule universe. *Journal of chemical information and modeling*, Vol. 55, 3 (2015), 529--537.
- [3] Fabian et al., "Molecular representation learning with language models and domain-relevant auxiliary tasks," *Machine Learning for Molecules Workshop @ NeurIPS 2020*, Nov. 2020, [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2011.13230>
- [4] Honda, S. Shi, and H. R. Ueda, "SMILES Transformer: Pre-trained Molecular Fingerprint for Low Data Drug Discovery," Nov. 2019, [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1911.04738>
- [5] Izhar Wallach, Michael Dzamba, and Abraham Heifets. 2015. AtomNet: a deep convolutional neural network for bioactivity prediction in structure-based drug discovery. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1510.02855* (2015).
- [6] Jianping Liu, Xiujuan Lei, Yuchen Zhang, Yi Pan, The prediction of molecular toxicity based on BiGRU and GraphSAGE, *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, Volume 153, 2023,106524, ISSN 0010-4825, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combiomed.2022.106524>.
- [7] J. Li and X. Jiang, "Mol-BERT: An Effective Molecular Representation with BERT for Molecular Property Prediction," *Wirel Commun Mob Comput*, vol. 2021, 2021, doi: 10.1155/2021/7181815.
- [8] Korshunova M, B. Ginsburg, A. Tropsha, and O. Isayev, "OpenChem: A Deep Learning Toolkit for Computational Chemistry and Drug Design," *J Chem Inf Model*, vol. 61, no. 1, pp. 7–13, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1021/acs.jcim.0c00971.
- [9] Li H, Sze K-H, Lu G, Ballester PJ (2021) Machine-learning scoring functions for structure-based virtual screening. *WIREs Comput Mol Sci* 11(1):e1478
- [10] Luo J, Hu B, Hu M, Zhao Y, Liu TL (2019) Status and prospects of organic redox flow batteries toward sustainable energy storage. *ACS Energy Lett* 4(9):2220–2240
- [11] Mayr, et al., Large-scale comparison of machine learning methods for drug target prediction on chembl, *Chem. Sci.* 9 (2018) 5441–5451.
- [12] N. Wen, G. Liu, J. Zhang, R. Zhang, Y. Fu, and X. Han, "A fingerprints based molecular property prediction method using the BERT model," *J Cheminform*, vol. 14, no. 1, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1186/s13321-022-00650-3.
- [13] Ramsundar B, P. Eastman, P. Walters and V. Pande, *Deep Learning for the Life Sciences: Applying Deep Learning to Genomics, Microscopy, Drug Discovery, and More*, O'Reilly Media, Sebastopol, CA, 1st edition., 2019.
- [14] Sheng Wang, Jiawen Yao, Zheng Xu, and Junzhou Huang. 2016. Subtype Cell Detection with an Accelerated Deep Convolution Neural Network International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention. Springer, 640--648.
- [15] Sherstinsky, Fundamentals of recurrent neural network (rnn) and long short-term memory (lstm) network, *Phys. D: Nonlinear Phenom.* 404 (2020) 132306.
- [16] Simeon et al., "Probing the origins of human acetylcholinesterase inhibition via QSAR modeling and molecular docking," *PeerJ*, vol. 2016, no. 9, 2016, doi: 10.7717/PEERJ.2322.

- [17] Stokes JM, Yang K, Swanson K, Jin W, Cubillos-Ruiz A, Donghia NM, MacNair CR, French S, Carfrae LA, Bloom-Ackermann Z, Tran VM, Chiappino-Pepe A, Badran AH, Andrews IW, Chory EJ, Church GM, Brown ED, Jaakkola TS, Barzilay R, Collins JJ (2020) A deep learning approach to antibiotic discovery. *Cell* 181(2):475–483.
- [18] Zhongxing Peng, Zheng Xu, and Junzhou Huang 2016. RSPiRiT: Robust self-consistent parallel imaging reconstruction based on generalized Lasso Biomedical Imaging (ISBI), 2016 IEEE 13th International Symposium on. IEEE, 318--321.
- [19] Z. Xu, S. Wang, F. Zhu, J. Huang, Seq2seq fingerprint: an unsupervised deep molecular embedding for drug discovery, in: Proceedings of the 8th ACM International Conference on Bioinformatics, Computational Biology, and Health Informatics, 2017, pp.285–294.
- [20] Zhenqin & Ramsundar, Bharath & Feinberg, Evan N & Gomes, Joseph & Geniesse, Caleb & Pappu, Aneesh & Leswing, Karl & Pande, Vijay. (2017). MoleculeNet: A Benchmark for Molecular Machine Learning. *Chemical Science*. 9. 10.1039/C7SC02664A.
- [21] Zhang, Ru & Lin, Yanmei & Wu, Yijia & Deng, Lei & Zhang, Hao & Liao, Mingzhi & Peng, Yuzhong. (2024). MvMRL: a multi-view molecular representation learning method for molecular property prediction. *Briefings in bioinformatics*. 25. 10.1093/bib/bbae298.
- [22] Jeong, Mswahili, Medard & Hwang, JunHa & Rajapakse, Jagath & Jo, Kyuri & Jeong, Young-Seob. (2025). Positional embeddings and zero-shot learning using BERT for molecular-property prediction. *Journal of Cheminformatics*. 17. 10.1186/s13321-025-00959-9.
- [23] Xinqi , Li, Jiashan & Gong. (2024). Harnessing Pre-trained Models for Accurate Prediction of Protein-Ligand Binding Affinity. 10.21203/rs.3.rs-5382178/v1.
- [24] Zizhang chen & Hong, Pengyu & Madireddy, Sandeep. (2024). Question Rephrasing for Quantifying Uncertainty in Large Language Models: Applications in Molecular Chemistry Tasks. 10.48550/arXiv.2408.03732.